

D5.5 GUIDELINES FOR TRACER PRINTING IN PACKAGING FOR EFFECTIVE SORTING, MANAGEMENT AFTER USE

WORK PACKAGE 5

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T5.5 Printing of registered tracers to enable
identification and management after use

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	
Ballard Haut (Skin)	Thin copper-layer on gravure cylinder carrying the printing cells
CFP	CIRCULAR Food Pack
DDP	Deinking- & Delamination-Primer
KIT	Karlsruhe Institute of Technology
MDO-PE	Machine-direction orientated Polyethylene
NC	Nitrocellulose
OPV	Overprint varnish = lacquer
PCR	Post-Consumer Recyclate
PE	Polyethylene
POLY	Polysecure GmbH
PU or PUR	Polyurethane

PUBLISHABLE EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

CIRCULAR FoodPack aims to facilitate the circular use of plastic packaging, specifically addressing the most sensitive product category: food packaging. One of the main objectives in the project was to design, develop and upscale sortable and fully recyclable flexible packaging materials with post-consumer polyethylene recyclates (PE PCR).

The approach to achieving recyclability focuses on the use of polyethylene (PE)-based mono-material multilayer laminate structures designed for flexible food packaging applications. According to the European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) requirements, PE PCRs intended for use in flexible food packaging must be produced from food packaging input waste. Therefore, to enable closed-loop recycling of these recyclable food packaging materials after their end-of-life, it is necessary to sort them out of a mixed food- and non-food post-consumer waste streams.

This sorting process is achieved through the implementation of Tracer-Based-Sorting (TBS) technology. The TBS technology enables the separation of food packaging items from non-food packaging with a sorting purity of 99% by applying fluorescent tracer particles to flexible packaging. The sorted food packaging items are then recycled, and the resulting PE PCRs are reintegrated into the newly designed flexible food packaging materials. Within the CIRCULAR Food-Pack project, this has been successfully achieved by embedding PE PCR layer between two functional barrier layers of the packaging laminate.

The tracers are integrated into the laminate structure so that they are easily detectable during the sorting process, do not compromise the intended use of the packaging as food-safe, and can be removed during subsequent recycling processes. This is accomplished by incorporating the tracers into the printing inks, which are later removed through deinking processes also developed in the project.

This deliverable includes findings regarding the printability of the newly developed tracers after mixing them with printing inks. Various printing techniques were screened, including gravure, flexo, and inkjet printing. Gravure printing has been identified as the most suitable technology for the application of tracer-containing inks.

Considering the location of the tracer-printed layer within the laminate, both surface printing and reverse printing are viable options. However, reverse printing is advantageous due to superior scratch resistance and improved surface finish.

Guidelines have been established for tracer printing in flexible packaging, ensuring the effective sorting of food packaging items at the end of their life cycle. These guidelines address the optimal location of tracers within the flexible packaging laminate, the type and concentration of tracer used, particle size, the selection of appropriate ink binders and the suitable printing processes.

1. INTRODUCTION

To facilitate a closed-loop recycling system for food-grade flexible plastic packaging, both design-for-recycling and design-from-recycling aspects must be addressed. In the CIRCULAR Food-Pack project, we propose the application of fluorescent tracers to enable high-quality sorting of food-grade packaging items from post-consumer flexible packaging waste streams.

From a design-from-recycling perspective, the method of applying tracers to packaging must integrate seamlessly into the packaging production. This approach should be compatible with both recycled and virgin input materials. From a design-for-recycling point of view, it is essential that the tracers be fully removable during the post-consumer recycling process to prevent sorting errors in subsequent use cycles.

Both aspects can be addressed by incorporating the tracers in printing inks and applying them within the regular design print, using common printing techniques. For consumer packaging applications, printing tracers onto the surface is generally preferred over incorporating them into polymer films via a masterbatch. Printing offers higher versatility and flexibility, since tracer codes and material composition/layer structure can be adjusted independently. Additionally, since the tracers are part of the print layer, they do not come into contact with the packaging contents¹.

Applying the tracers in a print layer also allows for their removal during the deinking process. Therefore, a critical requirement for the printing inks used is that they must be deinkable in the deinking processes developed within the project.

Polysecure (POLY), Siegwirk and AMCOR screened the tracers developed by Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT) and POLY for coatability and printability and tested basic stability in printing applications. Siegwirk evaluated the usability of these tracers across various printing technologies commonly employed for packaging materials. The application properties of tracer-containing inks were investigated, as well as alternative ways of application methods via lacquers or overprint varnishes.

2. USABILITY OF TRACERS IN INKS

2.1. Tracer properties and requirements

As part of the project, POLY, in collaboration with Siegwirk, investigated the required tracer area concentration and coverage needed for reliable identification using state-of-the-art NIR sorters for different types of tracers. The experimental results have been reported in Deliverable D2.4 (confidential) and the conclusions thereof have been condensed into a guideline on using tracers in print for flexible packaging in Deliverable D3.8, "Guidelines on Design for Recycling" (public).

To summarize, the minimum required tracer area concentration in the ink was determined to be 20 µg/cm² when mixed into white or yellow pigmented ink on a white background. In darker

¹ This requirement is not critical since for the tracer system mainly used in the project, conformity with the EU regulations for food contact has been declared, and food-contact approval by the FDA (U.S. Food and Drug Administration) has been granted.

ink colours, the concentration may have to be increased to compensate the additional absorption. Regarding the minimum size for an individual detectable spot of tracer print, a contiguous patch of at least a dot with a 10 mm diameter or a square of 10 mm x 10 mm or similar is necessary and sufficient. If the patch size is smaller, the tracer concentration can be increased for compensation (to some extent). Feature sizes smaller than 5 mm cannot be considered as detectable at all due to the resolution of current NIR sorters. Such a patch must be applied on every side of the object that may possibly face upwards on the conveyor belt. Therefore, the total necessary area of tracer print depends on the packaging geometry. Areas larger than the minimum size or additional patches are advisable to increase the likelihood of the detection in case of obfuscation by dirt, overlaying objects or folding/crumpling of the object. This visibility should be maintained even if the packaging item becomes soiled, flattened, folded, crumpled, or fragmented during use and disposal. General recommendation for flat items is to use at least double the minimum tracer area, or two patches, to ensure visibility from all sides. The areas likely to fold inward in a pouch should be avoided for printing the tracers.

Tracer particle size and effect on printability:

The printing ink can be seen as a kind of vehicle to “transport” the color pigments and the tracer particles, of which the particle size plays a crucial role as it impacts the printability. Therefore, further attention is required to this parameter when it comes to the usability of tracers in different printing processes like flexo-, gravure-, screen-, inkjet- and offset-printing used for printing of packaging. POLY has assessed the particle size of tracers developed in the project and is constantly monitoring this parameter for tracers in commercial production. Generally, the particle size of tracers intended for sorting purposes can be considered as a statistical distribution with most particles being in the range of 1-10 μm . The size distribution can be tuned to a certain degree by variation of synthesis parameters or by sieving. **Post-production milling, however, should be avoided as it impacts the luminescence properties.** A general value for the D50 diameter² (50% quantile of the distribution) is 5-6 μm and for the D95 diameter 9-10 μm . Typically, the D50 value for an ink containing colored pigments or titanium dioxide as a white pigment is well below 1 μm . Therefore, the usability of tracers in different printing processes depends on the specific process and the conditions under which the ink is transferred to the substrate. These aspects are discussed in detail in Section 2.2.

2.2. Printing processes

Some of the possible printing technologies commonly used in the industry and therefore considered in the project for the application of tracer-including inks are described in this section with their advantages and disadvantages.

- **Gravure printing**

In gravure printing, inks are transferred using a printing cylinder. The ink must fill the engraved cells on the cylinder, which then transfers the liquid ink to the substrate. Subsequently, the solvent is removed during thermal drying. The ink must meet processing requirements, such as having the appropriate viscosity to fill the cells and release them upon

² Volume or mass-based particle diameter, as obtained by static light scattering method

contact with the substrate. Additionally, all ink components must fit into the cells to be transferred. For instance, if a pigment particle is too large, it will not fit into the cylinder cells. The cell-dimensions depend on the design. For a full-tone printing area, the cell dimensions typically range from 120 μm to 180 μm diagonally and approximately 48 μm in depth. However, for more detailed designs, the cell dimensions decrease significantly, with the cell depths potentially reaching 10 μm or less. Figure 1 shows the cell shape in gravure printing. In this figure, Winkelung is for angling. Grossnapf refers to a large cell. Quernapf is the cell that has been engraved or formed in a transverse direction relative to the cylinder's axis or the direction of printing. Längsnapf is a longitudinally shaped gravure cell, meaning the cell is elongated along the direction of printing (the machine direction). Kleinnapf cells (small cells) are for fine details.

In applications with low print density, only particles smaller than the threshold determined by the cell size can be transferred, resulting in a lower-than-expected tracer concentration. This effect should be carefully evaluated when planning such designs.

Figure 1: Cell shape in gravure printing. (source: Siegwirk internal training files)

- **Flexo printing**

In flexo printing, the dimensions of the cells in the anilox roller (see Figure 2) are the limiting factor, while the size of the dots on the printing plate restricts the particle size of the pigments. Furthermore, the ink in the flexo printing process undergoes two stages of ink splitting: first when transferred from the anilox roller to the printing plate, and second when transferred from the printing plate to the substrate. Therefore, the issue of 'dusting' must be considered. In particular, inks with a high pigment load, such as a white ink with 40-50% pigment content, are prone to dusting and should be considered highly loaded.

Figure 2: Scheme of flexo-printing (source: Wikipedia CC BY-SA3.0)

- **Inkjet printing**

Another printing technique is inkjet printing, in which the ink must pass through nozzles with dimensions in the range of several hundred nanometers. All ink components need to be smaller than the nozzle dimensions to avoid clogging. As a result, inkjet printing is generally unsuitable for inks containing tracer particles larger than a few microns.

- **Screen Printing**

Screen printing can work well with tracer inks, although this technique is not commonly used for producing flexible packaging materials. In this process, a mesh is used to apply paste ink, with a rubber doctor blade pushing the ink through the mesh. Areas where the mesh is blocked remain unprinted. While effective, this technique is labor-intensive and therefore not the most efficient solution for large-scale flexible packaging applications. The mesh dimensions, which are the limiting factor for the particle size, typically are in the order of millimeters, thus being well suitable for the printing of tracers.

- **Offset printing**

The size of the tracer particles is at the limit for offset printing (with particles up to approximately 10 μm being transferable). POLY has successfully evaluated this technology with their tracers outside of this project, indicating no issues with using this technique. However, potential problems with reduced particle transfer at low print densities, as described above, should still be considered.

Conclusion for the tracer application by means of different printing processes, and the guidelines regarding the print size

In flexible packaging production, gravure and flexo printing dominate the market. During the project, we successfully evaluated gravure printing as feasible for packaging production trials. Additionally, POLY successfully tested the usage of tracers in both flexo and offset printing.

Based on the results, large-scale packaging production within the project utilized gravure printing technology, including tracer-containing inks in the production trials at AMCOR. The print layouts were designed to include sufficient areas with high print density, ensuring that reduced particle transfer in small cells would not affect the sorting process. Overall, within the current setup, the tracers are expected to be compatible with all printing-techniques except digital inkjet printing.

2.3. Protrusion of tracers in printed material

The pigment or in this case the tracer should not protrude too much from the printed layer, as such particles could be easily scratched off. If the material is to be laminated, the size of the pigments also affects the adhesive usage, as the surface must be completely wetted. If not, optical defects may occur in the laminated structure. In gravure and flexo-printing, the biggest known components are white pigments, matting agents and wax-particles, with dimensions typically ranging from 1 to 5 μm . The usual layer thicknesses of the dried ink in these printing techniques are provided in Table 1.

Table 1: The thickness of dry ink layer based on the printing technology used, measured by microtome cuts (source: Siegwirk internal data)

Printing technique	Thickness of dry ink-layer [μm]
Flexo printing	0.8 - 3.0
Gravure printing	1.5 - 5.0
Screen printing	Up to 15 (and more)
Offset-printing	1.0 – 3.0
Inkjet printing	1.0 – 2.0

Therefore, in all techniques except screen printing, a significant amount of tracer particles may protrude from the ink layer. However, perfect smoothness is generally not required. As long as the particles are securely bound in the layer and lamination can occur without defects, some surface irregularities are tolerable. It has been determined that both surface and reverse printing of tracer-infused inks in a laminate are possible. If the tracer is used in a surface-printed structure, the use of an overprint varnish (OPV) is strongly recommended to protect the tracer from being scratched off. In a laminated structure, the films cover the tracer particles, and no further precautions are necessary. However, in reverse printing, the top polymer layer and any printed layers above should be transparent in the relevant NIR range³.

2.4. Visual appearance of tracer-containing prints

Apart from mechanical properties, visual appearance quality of printed designs must be maintained when using tracer-containing inks. As discussed before, large tracer particles may protrude from the dried print layer, possibly causing the appearance of an additional surface roughness compared to ink layers without tracer. Figure 3 shows the visual appearance of printed PE foils with and without tracer. In these samples, the tracer is included in the white ink layer. The print is covered with an overprint varnish for scratch protection. As a worst-case demonstration, the shown samples contain a tracer with especially large particle sizes of up to 100 μm . (The

³ 900 nm – 1700 nm. Transparency in the visible range is not required.

actual maximum particle size in the print may be determined by the printing process, as discussed in section 2.2). Nevertheless, no visual surface roughness of the white ink layer incorporating tracer particles can be observed. The visual appearance of surfaces with and without tracer, as observed both from the top and the bottom side, is the same.

Figure 3: Visual appearance of light reflections on printed test sheets with and without tracer. The print layer structure is: PE foil, blue color (on one half of the surface only), white color, overprint varnish. Left pictures: Inks without any tracer. Right column: Tracers included in white color layer. Top row: View as seen in reverse printing (print layers below foil). Bottom row: View as seen in surface printing (color layers on top of PE foil). No significant difference in surface roughness between tracer-containing and non-tracer-containing prints can be observed.

2.5. Effective incorporation of tracers into inks

Pigments in their delivery form are larger than those used in the printing process due to agglomeration. In general, a grinding process is performed before printing, where the grinding device breaks the agglomerates into smaller particles. These smaller particles need to be encapsulated by the binder, which stabilises the pigment. Figure 4 depicts the visual effect change between unmilled and milled particles.

Figure 4: Relation between particle size and optical impression of pigments. Left less saturated and right higher saturated color. (source: Siegwerk internal training files)

In terms of incorporation into an ink system, tracers can be seen as pigments used as colorants in printing inks. The grinding of a pigment to incorporate it in a lacquer or printing ink requires specific machinery and processes. The most commonly used equipment includes high-speed stirrers with a tooth-blade or rotor-stator-geometry, as well as pearl-mills. The choice of machinery depends on factors such as the pigment's size, amount, and wettability, as well as the binder-system (resin) used. In flexible packaging, the most commonly used binder systems today are polyurethane (PU) and nitrocellulose (NC). It is known that the mechanical recycling of packaging material printed with NC-based inks can be problematic, and it may turn out that the NC binder system has limited usability for mechanical recycling. A recently published guideline for recycling by RecyClass classifies NC as "limited compatible at best" (yellow or red category), whereas other binder-chemistries such as PU, are considered fully compatible with recycling⁴.

Therefore, the best choice is to use PU as the binder system. Pigment grinding in PU is usually performed using two different grinding devices: a high-speed stirrer for inorganic pigments, such as titanium dioxide, and a pearl mill for organic pigments.

Pigments that are not properly encapsulated tend to re-agglomerate and settle. The amount of binder and pigment must be properly balanced. The appearance of the colour is also related to the particle size (surface) of the pigments. Generally, smaller particle sizes result in more saturated colours (see Figure 4).

2.5.1. Tracer sedimentation: Causes

Similar to pigments, tracer particles also face issues with agglomeration and sedimentation in liquid environments. Sedimentation is particularly accelerated by the relatively high specific density of the particles. Generally, tracers with larger particle sizes exhibit a stronger tendency to sediment. However, differences in sedimentation behaviour can also result from variations in particle geometry, such as those caused by a tendency to form agglomerates. Milling experiments on the tracers conducted at POLY and KIT have shown that a minimum particle size is

⁴ <https://recyclclass.eu/recyclability/design-for-recycling-guidelines/>

required for the tracers to function properly. Due to the special doping of the ceramic structure, the particle size of the tracers should be above 5-6 μm . Smaller particles reduce the luminescence efficiency. Therefore, additional milling steps after the tracer production should generally be avoided. This causes certain limitations for the incorporation of the tracers into printing inks. The grinding conditions must not be too harsh to avoid damaging the ceramic pigment. Thus, only a high-speed stirrer should be used, similar to the process for white pigment dispersion. If a certain amount of binder has already been “captured” by the white pigments, stabilising the additional tracer pigment becomes more difficult. As a result, the higher the load of “conventional” pigment and tracer-pigment, the less binder is available in the ink, leading to increased sedimentation.

2.5.2. How to avoid sedimentation

Sedimentation is a common challenge when incorporating tracers or pigments into ink systems, especially when dealing with particles of specific sizes. To prevent or minimize sedimentation, there are two primary strategies to consider:

1. Adjusting the Rheology of the Ink (Thixotropic Approach):

One potential method to combat sedimentation is by modifying the rheology of the ink. By making the ink thixotropic or structurally viscous, the ink’s consistency changes depending on the application of shear forces. In its resting state, the ink becomes thicker, almost like a 'pudding,' while shear forces from the stirring, pumping, or doctor blade action return it to a liquid state. This approach can reduce sedimentation, as the higher viscosity helps keep the particles suspended. However, it does come with certain trade-offs. Printers often find thixotropic inks challenging because they affect viscosity measurement and the handling of the ink, leading to issues like dead zones in the printing press. Therefore, this approach should be tested carefully to ensure it does not negatively impact the overall printing process.

2. Using a Masterbatch (Pigment Concentrate) and Optimizing Dispersion:

The classic method of tackling sedimentation involves the creation of a masterbatch, which is a pigment concentrate. In this method, the binder surrounds the pigment, facilitating a more stable interaction between the pigment and the solvent. Typically, this is achieved by grinding or dispersing the pigment and binder together. However, this process has limitations, especially when dealing with tracers. Tracers require a specific particle size to ensure proper functionality. If the particle size is too small or too large, it can affect the balance between the binder’s adhesion and the pigment’s buoyancy, leading to sedimentation. The key is to strike a balance between the particle size, the binder’s strength, and the pigment’s buoyancy force. The smaller the particles, the greater the surface area, which generally improves buoyancy and reduces sedimentation. However, there are physical limitations to how small the particles can be made without compromising the tracers’ effectiveness.

In conclusion, to achieve a stable and repeatable process in industrial applications, the parameters of the mixing/stirring process and the ratios of binder to color and tracer pigments must be carefully optimized for each individual tracer-color recipe. Both the rheology of the ink and the dispersion process need to be adjusted to minimize sedimentation while maintaining ink performance and tracer effectiveness. While using thixotropic agents can help improve sedimentation control, it is important to consider the potential impact on the printing process. Creating a stable

masterbatch with the right particle size and binder system can also help maintain particle suspension, but this must be optimized to prevent any negative effects on ink performance. Ultimately, both approaches require careful testing and adjustment to ensure the best results in ink stability and functionality.

2.6. Assessment of printing inks with tracers for large-scale trials

2.6.1. Abrasion test

Based on experience, Siegwirk knows that inorganic pigments, such as titanium dioxide (white) and silicon dioxide (matting agent), tend to be abrasive. This abrasiveness can cause wear on press parts that come into direct contact with the printing inks, such as doctor blades, printing cylinders, and anilox rollers. Since the tracers provided by POLY are also inorganic, their abrasive tendency needed to be evaluated.

The abrasion test at Siegwirk is conducted using a Brugger device (see Figure 5). The device consists of four doctor blades (shown as Raket in Figure 5) that rotate over a cylinder surface, with printing ink flooding the test chamber. The amount of rotation corresponds to that of a printing cylinder in a press. By optically comparing the damage patterns on the cylinder surface, an indication of abrasivity is provided.

Figure 5: Sample of the abrasion testing plate (source: actual performed test at Siegwirk)

Siegwerk tested the tracer incorporated into a white ink and an unpigmented extender, which are used to produce CIRCULAR FoodPack demo material for large-scale printing at AMCOR. An extender is an unpigmented ink typically used to adjust the color strength of colored printing inks or as an overprint varnish (OPV). It consists of the binder and relevant additives (e.g., adhesion promoters). An extender is the ideal medium for testing abrasion, as no other pigments interfere with the Ballard-skin (shown as "Verchromte Ballardhaut in Figure 5) or doctor blades.

The measurements in Table 2 show the decrease of weight of the Ballard-skin (test-panel) resulting from the abrasion caused by the ink-particles between doctor blade & Ballard-skin.

Table 2: The decrease in the weight of the Ballard-skin resulting from the abrasion (source: Siegwerk – internal data of Quality Control tests)

Ink particles	Decrease of weight
UR29 white (reference)	7.3 mg (after 1 million revolutions)
UR29 white with tracer (tracer amount for 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$)	5.8 mg (after 1 million revolutions)
UR42-3 extender (ref.)	0.35 mg (after 1.8 million revolutions)
UR42-3 extender with tracer (tracer amount for 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$)	3.49 mg (after 1.8 million revolutions)

The tracers from POLY exhibit a certain level of abrasivity, as shown by the results of the extender-trial. However, the evaluation of the white ink with tracers does not indicate any significant increase in abrasive properties. The tracers perform similarly to a regular white pigment, meaning that no issues should arise during the printing process (e.g., damage to cylinders). This behaviour was confirmed during the large-scale printing trials conducted at AMCOR, where no exceptional damage to the Yellow-cylinder was observed.

2.6.2. Sedimentation test

For incorporating tracers into printing inks, it is essential to use a high-speed stirrer instead of an intensive grinding process. This is because the small particle size of the tracers can degrade their luminescence effect if subjected to harsh grinding. However, it should be noted that the encapsulation of the tracer pigments with the binder may not be perfect, and sedimentation of the tracer particles is expected.

In preparation for large-scale printing trials at AMCOR, Siegwerk received several tracer versions from KIT and POLY, each with different fluorescence properties, resulting in distinct tracer codes. All of these versions showed some tendency for sedimentation, but the best behavior was observed with the **Holmium (Ho)**-based tracer. The sedimentation time for the Ho tracer was measured in hours, indicating that sedimentation is not a critical issue. Consequently, printing inks doped with the Ho tracer were well-suited for large-scale print jobs, and this tracer exhibited the highest luminescence efficiency among those evaluated.

The optimal concentration for the Ho tracer was found to be between **20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$** and **50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$** on a white or yellow background. The lower limit of this concentration range (20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) represents the minimum area concentration, while the upper limit (50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$) is determined by the ink viscosity. This maximum concentration may vary depending on the ink type and process parameters, so for different ink formulations, it may be necessary to re-evaluate this concentration accordingly.

On the other hand, during the print-run at AMCOR, the **Erbium (Er)**-based tracer exhibited significant sedimentation in the ink-duct, which resulted in a lower-than-expected amount of

tracer being transferred onto the printed material. A demonstration of the sedimentation behavior is shown in Figure 6. The sedimentation led to a decrease in luminescence intensity, and as a result, the Erbium-based tracer was not detectable by state-of-the-art NIR sorters during a test conducted in November 2023 at the Steinert pilot sorting line. However, the tracer was still detectable with a higher-sensitivity measurement device used at POLY.

Given these results, further investigation and optimization of the Erbium tracer's particle properties and of the production and processing of tracer-inks with Er tracers are required to ensure its usability in flexible packaging production.

Figure 6: Sample of UR42-3 extender with Erbium-based tracer, showing sedimentation after unstirred storage (lighter white area at the bottom of the container as indicated by the black line).

3. USABILITY OF TRACERS IN OTHER COATINGS

The tracer concept is versatile and extends beyond printing inks, offering potential for use in other components of flexible packaging, such as films, adhesives, and uncolored coatings (e.g. overprint varnishes, OPVs). Below are the key considerations and best practices for incorporating tracers into various coating applications:

Incorporation into Films: Incorporating tracers directly into the polymer matrix during the film extrusion process is feasible. The effectiveness of this approach depends on the application. Since tracers remain functional in the recyclate and are not removed during deinking in the recycling process, they can be beneficial in closed-loop recycling systems. In such systems, the same tracer can be reused, contributing to a more sustainable process. However, for typical packaging markets, removable solutions are preferred as they offer more flexibility in the recycling process.

Incorporation into Adhesives and Coatings: Tracers can also be used in adhesives or uncolored coatings like overprint varnishes (OPV). Siegwirk has investigated this application with tracers in their powder form (as shown in Figure 7). When incorporated into clear products, such as

OPVs or adhesives, the tracer can sometimes be visible or detectable when a certain concentration is applied to a transparent film. Here are the key guidelines for using tracers in coatings:

- The maximum amount of tracer that can be incorporated without it being visibly detectable is approximately $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, with OPV applied at a normal usage range (1.0 gsm dry) (see Figure 8, left picture).
- When the tracer concentration exceeds approximately 1.5 gsm/100 g of ink, a certain haze in the coating may become noticeable (see Figure 8, right picture). It is up to the customer to determine if this haze is acceptable for the specific application.
- For highly transparent films, it is likely that the required application weight will exceed $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ if detection by current NIR sorters is targeted. However, more sensitive detection devices may allow for concentrations at or below $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ to be sufficient.

Figure 7: Delivery form of the tracer to the partners in powder form

Figure 8. MDOPE substrates coated with inks including tracers. Left: the tracer concentration is at $10 \mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$, and right: the tracer concentration is above the threshold

Recommendation for Optimal Tracer Application: To enhance the luminescence effect and minimize the required tracer concentrations, it is recommended to incorporate tracers in white matrices or on a white background. This approach improves the visibility of the tracers during sorting and detection and ensures the tracer's effectiveness with reduced concentrations.

By adhering to these guidelines, tracers can be effectively incorporated into various coatings and film applications, maintaining their functionality while minimizing visual interference and ensuring compatibility with sorting systems.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Siegwerk has screened five different types of tracers developed by KIT and POLY, evaluating their performance when mixed into printing inks. These tracers were tested for coatability, printability, optical emission, and basic stability. Based on these evaluations, the following conclusions were drawn for effective tracer use in flexible packaging, particularly for sorting and recycling purposes:

Printing Technology Selection: The effect of several printing techniques, including gravure, flexo, screen, offset, inkjet, and digital printing, were assessed for sorting performance. Gravure printing emerged as the most suitable method for the tracer ink formulation, as its cell size on the printing cylinder matched well with the ink's characteristics, such as viscosity, solid content, and particle size. Flexo and offset printing were also effective but not to the same extent as gravure. Inkjet printing was found unsuitable due to limitations related to ink particle size and clogging.

Tracer Placement and Ink Formulation: The optimal location for tracers in packaging was found to be within the printing ink itself. Tracers incorporated into adhesives or primer layers performed less effectively. The tracers performed best when mixed with white pigments in the ink binder, or with yellow-pigmented ink applied to a white background. The tracer type, concentration, and particle size were carefully optimized to match the ink formulation and selected printing process. Among the tracers, the Holmium (Ho)-based tracer proved to be the most effective.

Surface vs. Reverse Printing: Both surface and reverse printing were found to be viable options depending on tracer placement within the laminate. However, reverse printing (under a top coating or MDOPE substrate) was primarily chosen for this project to avoid limitations related to pasteurization or steam sterilization (e.g., in ambient ready meals or wet pet food). The project focused on reverse printing using gravure technology to ensure compatibility with a wide range of packaging applications.

Tracer Concentration and Printed Area Size: The minimum effective concentration of tracers in the ink was found to be 20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{cm}^2$ when mixed with white or yellow pigmented inks on a white background. The minimum size for the individual printed area was a 10 mm diameter dot or a square with a 10 mm edge length. It is not problematic if the printed area does not fully cover the surface, as long as the tracer concentration requirements are met in the printed area.

Integration into Flexible Packaging: The tracers developed in the project were successfully incorporated into newly designed mono-material PE-based flexible packaging laminates. These laminates, containing both tracers and PE PCR (post-consumer recycled material), were produced in collaboration with AMCOR, with over 1000 meters produced for testing. The laminates, containing tracers, were further converted into coffee pouches for their eventual recycling within the CIRCULAR FoodPack process chain, demonstrating the tracers' potential for use in the circular economy.

This performed work sets the foundation for using tracers in packaging materials to improve sorting, recycling and management processes post-use, making significant contributions to sustainability and recycling efficiency in the flexible packaging industry.

